

A Report on Column Generation With Numerical Example

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Report Summary

Column Generation (Delayed Column Generation) is an algorithm for solving integer linear programming (ILP) and mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problems with a large number of variables (columns). This algorithm was first applied by Gilmore and Gomory to solve a large, real-life cutting stock problem. Since then, several researchers have exploited its advantages and applied this technique to many real-life applications.

The report begins by introducing the concept of column generation and discussing the challenges associated with large optimization problems. It then explains the theory behind column generation, using the cutting stock problem as an example, and explores various solution approaches. The report also highlights how the column generation approach is mathematically distinct from the simplex algorithm, focusing on a comparison of the pricing step in both methods. The branch-and-price method, and how it can be used in conjunction with column generation, is explained in the later part of the report.

Lastly, a numerical illustration is provided to offer a thorough understanding of the concepts and methods discussed.

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Chapter 1: Idea of Column Generation

Linear programs occurring in practice can be extremely large. For large LPs, the vast majority of the matrix is superfluous. To solve a particular instance, we only need – constraints that are binding at optimality. Experience with large optimization problems indicates that usually, most of the columns never enter the basis. Usually, the number of extreme points (columns) are very large. Thus, we can afford not to ever generate these unused columns.

For Simplex methods, at any given iteration, only requires the current basic columns and the column which is to enter the basis. [1,2] Most of the variables are non-basic, which will take the value 0 in an optimal basic feasible solution. We need to check for variables that are basic at optimality. In fact, we only need constraints that have positive dual values and variables that have positive values at optimality. If we only had these variables and constraints from the start, we could solve them very easily. [1,3]

Consider the following *linear problem*. Now, it is convenient to consider the linear program (primal) to have equality constraints.

$$Z_{LP} := \max cx$$

such that

$$Ax = b, x \in R_+^n$$

Using representation theorem, Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k be the extreme points of the feasible region

The above problem can be reformulated as

$$\text{Min } \sum_{i=1}^k (cx_i) \alpha_i$$

Such that,

$$\sum_{i=1}^k (Ax_i) \alpha_i = b$$

Where,

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \dots + \alpha_k = 1 \quad \forall \quad \alpha_i \geq 0$$

This program is totally equivalent to the original linear program, but the variable of interest is α . In this program, all extreme points are called columns. Each column is a feasible solution of the original program and has a corresponding variable α_i for some i . Usually, the number of columns are very large and thus there are too many variables in this program.

Most of the variables are non-basic, which will take the value 0 in an optimal basic feasible solution. The main idea of the column generation method is to generate a column pool with a limited number of columns and consider only these columns in the program. Other variables are set to 0 automatically if their columns are not included in the column pool. An

optimal solution is found when all variables whose columns are not in the column pool have non-negative reduced costs. Before reaching the optimal solution, columns with negative reduced costs are continuously added to the column pool until no such column is found.

Key question: How to evaluate the reduced costs associated with all the non-basic columns and identify the entering column? The problem is that we do not know which variables and constraints these are. In problems with large numbers of variables, there are two main difficulties. [3]

- The time required just to generate the matrix.
- The time required to calculate the reduced costs for each iteration.

We can address both the above problems using delayed column generation.

We don't need to figure out the list of reduced costs for all the non-basic columns. Instead, in order to identify the entering column, it can be accomplished by solving another optimization. [8]

- Start with a subset of "promising" columns.
- Solve the LP with just these columns.
- Price the remaining columns and add those with negative reduced costs.
- Iterate.

In fact, we only need to find the column with the most negative reduced cost.

This is an optimization problem!

If we can solve this optimization problem, then we can solve the LP without explicitly listing every column.

Chapter 2: Theory of Column Generation

In order to find a successful solution of a large-scale mixed integer programming (MIP) problems, it requires solving linear programming (LP) relaxations that have huge number of variables. In subsequent iteration of simplex algorithm if the optimal solution is not achieved. The algorithm replaces one of the non-basic variables with a basic variable to improve objective function value in the next iteration. In problems involving huge number of variables (or columns), the explicit search of entering and leaving variable, sometimes becomes intractable. Gilmore and Gomory did propose an ingenious way to overcome this issue. [1,8] The Column Generation algorithm starts with a few columns by solving a master-subproblem and generates new columns when required. At first Gilmore and Gomory applied this algorithm to solve real life large scale cutting stock problem. Since then, several researchers have exploited its advantage and have applied this technique to many real-life applications. [13,14]

The column generation method is based on the theory of the basis and a representation theorem.

Let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k be the extreme points of the feasible region of the linear program and assume that the points in this feasible region are bounded. Then any feasible solution x can be expressed as a convex combination of the extreme points

$$x = \alpha_1 x_1 + \alpha_2 x_2 \dots + \alpha_k x_k$$

Where,

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \dots + \alpha_k = 1 \quad \forall \quad \alpha_i \geq 0$$

2.1 Cutting stock problem

In industries materials such as paper, textiles, metallic foil etc. are manufactured in rolls of fixed width (W), commonly termed as *raws*, and are subsequently cut into rolls of various small sized widths (w), termed as *finals*.

Manufacturers produce raws of a few standard widths. The numerous customers specify what should be the widths of the finals (it vary widely). This becomes an optimization problem (ILP) to find out what is the most economical way of cutting the existing raws into the desired finals, so that the least amount of left-overs are wasted or rather, least number of rolls are cut? [4,8,13,14]

Example: Consider example where the rows are 10cm in width, we need to fulfil the following summary of orders with different finals. Let a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 to be the finals of respective width.

Table 1

i	Quantity Required b_i	Width (w_i) in cm	Finals
1	9	3	a_1
2	79	5	a_2
3	90	6	a_3
4	27	9	a_4

Now we may speculate about various ways of filling the order summary. If the j^{th} pattern is used x_j times then we have.

Objective function

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum_{j=1}^n x_j$$

Such that

$$\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} x_j = b_i \quad \forall i$$

$$x_j \geq 0 \quad \forall j \in J$$

Here ($i=1,2,3,4$) and $N = 9, J = 5$. With b_i as mentioned in table 1.

Table 2

j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
a_{1j}	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	3
a_{2j}	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0
a_{3j}	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
a_{4j}	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Use	9	6	9	5	10	8	3	6	9
Left	1	3	1	5	0	2	7	4	1

Noting down that there is an obvious catch, an optimal solution of the mentioned problem may not be integer-valued and to provide a realistic plan, the numbers x_j must need to be a nonnegative integer.

Let us now think about the solution of the above integer program. One of the most obvious way is to relax the integrality constraints on the variables. In that case, the problem becomes a linear program which can be solved using standard algorithms such as the simplex algorithm.

2.2 Solution Approach: L. V. Kantorovich model

For solving the problem, the first thing we need is a formulation of problem as an integer program. One can be formed as follows. Suppose there are K raws. [4,5]

$$y_k's, k \in \{1 \dots K\}$$

y_k is assigned to 1 if k^{th} raw is cut; 0 otherwise. (We keep K binary)

We also keep $m \times K$ integer variables $x_{ik}'s, i \in \{1 \dots M\}$. x_{ik} is assigned to the number of times finals of width w_i is cut in roll k .

Minimize

$$z = \sum_{k=1}^K y_k$$

subject to

$$\sum_{k=1}^K x_{ik} \geq b_i, \quad i = 1 \dots m$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m w_i x_{ik} \leq W y_k, \quad k = 1 \dots K$$

$$y_k = 0 \text{ or } 1 \quad \forall k = 1..K$$

$$x_{ik} \geq 0$$

$$i = 1..m, k = 1..K \quad \& \quad x_{ik} \in \text{Integer}$$

The given formulation was introduced by Kantorovich. For solving the given example, we set $K = 9 + 79 + 90 + 27 = 215$ assuming at most one final is cut from one raw. We can set value of $K \geq 215$. In that case the all the extra variables y_k becomes 0 in the optimal solution.

Let us now think about the solution of the above integer program. One way is to relax the integrality constraints on the variables x_{ik} and y_k . In that case, the problem becomes a linear program which can be solved using standard algorithms such as simplex.

For given example, solution to the LP relaxation is 120.5 which is significantly less than the integer solution 157 (Having more finals, the gap increases). Hence just rounding the values of the variables in the optimum solution of the LP relaxation will be far from the integral solution.

2.3 Solution Approach: Gilmore-Gomory model

The solution improves significantly if we use the following trickier formulation introduced by Gilmore and Gomory. The possible cutting patterns are enumerated beforehand. The

patterns are described by the vector $(a_{1j}, \dots, a_{ij}, \dots, a_{mj})$ where element a_{ij} represents the number of rolls of width w_i obtained in cutting pattern j . Let x_j be a decision variable that designates the number of rolls to be cut according to cutting pattern j . [13,14]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize} \quad & z = \sum_{j \in J} x_j \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \sum_{j \in J} a_{ij} x_j \geq b_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \\ & x_j \geq 0 \quad \& \quad x_j \in \text{Integer} \quad \forall j \in J \end{aligned}$$

where J is the set of valid cutting patterns. For the given example, the valid cutting patterns are given in following table.

j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
a _{1j}	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	3
a _{2j}	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0
a _{3j}	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
a _{4j}	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Use	9	6	9	5	10	8	3	6	9
Left	1	3	1	5	0	2	7	4	1

(Now any cutting pattern that leaves 3cm or more of waste need not be considered because we could use the waste to obtain one or more 3cm final.)

Similar to the Kantorovich formulation, this can also be solved using the LP relaxation. However, values of x_j s (we say x_j^*) may not be all integer in the optimal solution of the LP relaxation. In that case, we can round each x_j^* down to the nearest integer and obtain a solution close to actual integer solution. The residual demands of finals which are not met due to rounding down can be found by brute-force.

For the given example, optimal LP solution $z = 156.7$ corresponds to $x_1^* = 27, x_2^* = 0, x_3^* = 90$ and $x_4^* = 39.5$. Rounding each x_j^* down to nearest integer gives value of $z = 157$ which fortunately matches with the optimal integer solution.

However, there are difficulties which originate from two different reasons:

- Problems commonly encountered in the paper or textiles industry may involve huge number of variables. For example, if the raw rolls are 200 cm. wide and if the finals are ordered in 40 different lengths ranging from 15cm. to 80cm. Then the number of different patterns may easily exceed 100 or even 100 million. In that case, the solution may not be tractable.
- Passing from an optimal *fractional-valued* solution to an optimal *integer-valued* solution is not easy neither accurate. Rounding the fractional values down and satisfying the residual demands, may not yield the optimal solution. If the finals are ordered in small enough quantities, then the patterns used in the optimal integer valued solution may be quite different from those used originally in the optimal fractional valued solutions.

Additional Example

Example: Consider an example where the raws are 17cm in width. We need to fulfil the following summary of orders with different finals. Let a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4 to be the finals of respective width.

i	Quantity Required b_i	Width (w_i) in cm	Finals
1	97	45	a_1
2	610	36	a_2
3	395	31	a_3
4	211	14	a_4

Now at first, we need to evaluate all the possible ways in which the raw can be cut into different finals. There are 37 possible ways.

(In the table j is the indices denote the ways or the pattern)

j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18
a_1j	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
a_2j	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
a_3j	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	0
a_4j	0	1	0	1	0	3	2	1	0	2	1	0	0	2	1	0	4	3
left	10	5	19	10	24	13	27	41	55	0	14	28	2	5	19	33	8	22

j	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37
a_1j	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
a_2j	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
a_3j	0	0	0	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
a_4j	2	1	0	0	2	1	0	4	3	2	1	0	7	6	5	4	3	2	1
left	36	50	64	7	10	24	38	13	27	41	55	69	2	16	30	44	58	72	86

Now any cutting pattern that leaves 14 cm or more of waste need not be considered because we could use the waste to obtain one or more 14cm final. $N=37, J=11$

An ingenious way of getting around the first difficulty was suggested by P. C. Gilmore and R. E. Gomory. The trick is to work with only a few patterns at a time and to generate new patterns only when they are really needed. This technique is called *delayed column generation*.

No efficient way of handling the second difficulty is known. However there have been instances of tackling this difficulty by using a method commonly known as *branch-and-price*. Here the trick is to combine the delayed column generation with the standard branch-and-bound algorithm for solving integer programs. Delayed column generation is applied to each node of the branch and bound tree to solve the LP subproblem.

Chapter 3: Comparison with Simplex

In this chapter, we touch upon the mathematical theory required to understand the basics of column generation. Starting with the mathematical interpretation of the simplex algorithm, particularly the step in which a non-basic variable replaces a basic variable to improve the cost.

3.1 Pricing step of Simplex Algorithm

In the simplex algorithm we start with an initial basic feasible solution, check whether it is optimal or not. If the solution is not optimal the algorithm works in such a way that in every step, one non-basic variable replaces one basic variable so that the value of the objective function improves. [5,6,12]

Let us call the following linear program the *master problem* (MP). Here it is convenient to consider the primal linear program with equality constraints.

$$Z_{LP} := \max cx$$

such that $Ax = b, x \in R_+^n$

Converting to dual it becomes $W_{LP} := \min ub$

such that $uA \geq c, u \in R^m$

We suppose that $\text{rank}(A) = m \leq n$, so that all the redundant equations have been removed from the LP. For solving the LP, in each iteration of the simplex method we look for a non-basic variable to price out and enter the basis. Column generation plays a key role in this pricing step. [6,7]

The algebra of pricing step is explained below as.

Let $A = (a_1 a_2 \dots a_n)$ where a_j is the j th column of A .

Since $\text{rank}(A) = m$, there exists a $m \times m$ nonsingular sub-matrix $A_B = (a_{B1} a_{B2} \dots a_{Bm})$

Let $J = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $B = \{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m\}$.

Now without loss of generality assume that the first m components of x are basic variables naming them as x_B . Now permute the columns of A so that $A = (A_B, A_N)$.

We can write $Ax = b$ as $A_B x_B + A_N x_N = b$

Where $x = (x_B x_N)$

Then a solution to $Ax = b$ is given by $x_B = A_B^{-1} b$ and $x_N = 0$

$$Ax = [A_B \ A_N] \begin{bmatrix} x_B \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = b$$

Or,

$$x_B = A_B^{-1}b$$

If x is a genuine corner (it is feasible) provided $x_B \geq 0$. Its cost is

$$cx = [c_B \ c_N] \begin{bmatrix} x_B \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = c_B A_B^{-1}b$$

Now, to proceed where to go next, after leaving this corner. The decision is made easy by elimination on A , which reduces the square part B to the identity matrix. In matrix notation this multiplies $Ax = b$ by A_B^{-1}

$$[I \ A_B^{-1}A_N] \begin{bmatrix} x_B \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = A_B^{-1}b$$

Now suppose, the non-basic (zero) components of x is increased to some non-zero value. Say x is changed to $x = [x'_B \ x'_N]$. To maintain equality the above equation becomes

$$[I \ A_B^{-1}A_N] \begin{bmatrix} x'_B \\ x'_N \end{bmatrix} = A_B^{-1}b$$

$$x'_B + A_B^{-1}A_N x'_N = A_B^{-1}b$$

$$x'_B = A_B^{-1}b - A_B^{-1}A_N x'_N$$

changes cost to

$$cx' = c_B x'_B + c_N x'_N = c_B (A_B^{-1}b - A_B^{-1}A_N x'_N) + c_N x'_N$$

Rearranging

$$cx' = c_B A_B^{-1}b + (c_N - c_B A_B^{-1}A_N) x'_N$$

The reduction in cost $cx' - cx$ is

$$c_B A_B^{-1}b + (c_N - c_B A_B^{-1}A_N) x'_N - c_B A_B^{-1}b = (c_N - c_B A_B^{-1}A_N) x'_N$$

We can see that as x_N increases, the cost function goes up or down depending on the sign of the vector \bar{c} in parentheses.

$$\bar{c} = c_N - c_B A_B^{-1}A_N$$

This vector contains the reduced costs. If $\bar{c} \geq 0$ then the current corner is optimal. The product $\bar{c}x_N$ in equation cannot be negative since $x \geq 0$. so the best decision is to keep $x_N = 0$ and stop. On the other hand, suppose a component is negative. Then the cost is reduced if the corresponding non-basic variable enters the basis. The simplex method chooses one entering variable the one with the most negative component of \bar{c} .

3.2 Pricing step in Delayed Column Generation

In each iteration of simplex method, we look for a non-basic variable to price out and enter the basis. That is, in the pricing step, given the dual vector $u = c_B A_B^{-1}$ we need to find the non-basic variable corresponding to which the reduced cost component is negative. One way to find this out is to calculate the minimum of all components of the reduced cost vector and take if it is negative. [5,7,8]

$$\arg \min \{ \bar{c}_j = c_j - u a_j , j \in N \}$$

where a_j is a column of matrix A . If the columns in A_B are also considered in calculating reduced cost vector, corresponding components in the reduced cost becomes zero.

Since,
$$c_B - c_B A_B^{-1} A_B = 0$$

Thus, inclusion of the basic columns does not change the decision. The previous equation can be re-written as.

$$\arg \min \{ \bar{c}_j = c_j - u a_j , j \in J \}$$

An explicit search of j from J may be computationally impossible when $|J|$ is huge. Gilmore and Gomory showed that the searching j from J explicitly is not necessary. If we look carefully, it is not j that we are interested. Rather we are interested in the column a_j that can replace one column of the basic matrix A_B . In practical applications, these columns often represent combinatorial objects such as paths, patterns, sets, permutations. They follow some embedded constraints i.e. $a_j \in A$, where A represents the constrained set. [9,10,11]

For example, in the cutting stock problem with Gilmore-Gomory formulation, each column represents a cutting pattern, which must satisfy the knapsack constraint - sum of widths of finals in a particular cutting pattern must not exceed the width of the raw rolls. Thus, in practice, one works with a reasonably small subset $J' \subset J$ of columns, with a *restricted master problem* (RMP).

If we have a feasible solution, let $\bar{\lambda}$ and \bar{u} be primal and dual optimal solutions of the RMP, respectively. When columns $a_j, j \in J$, are given as elements of a set A and the cost coefficient c_j can be computed from $a_j, c_j = c(a)$, then the subproblem

$$\bar{c}^* = \min \{ c(a) - \bar{u} a , a \in A \}$$

The above equation gives answer to the pricing problem. For the cutting stock problem, $c_j = 1, \forall j \in J$ and the set A is given by the constraint

$$\sum_{i=1}^m a_{ij} w_i \leq W, \quad \forall j \in J$$

Thus, for the cutting stock problem, the subproblem is

$$\max \sum_{i=1}^m \bar{u}_i a_i$$

Such that,

$$\sum_{i=1}^m a_i w_i \leq W$$

$$a_i \geq 0$$

This way of starting with a basic set of columns & generating more columns as and when necessary is known as *Delayed Column Generation* or simply *Column Generation*.

With the usual precautions against cycling of simplex method, column generation is finite and exact. In addition, it is possible to utilize the knowledge of intermediate solution quality during the process.

Let \bar{z} denote the optimal objective function value to the RMP.

Note by duality we have

$$\bar{z} = \bar{u}b$$

Interestingly, when an upper bound

i.e.
$$\kappa \geq \sum_{j \in J} \lambda_j$$

It holds for an optimal solution of the master problem, we establish not only an upper bound on z^* in each iteration, but also a lower bound. We cannot reduce \bar{z} by more than κ times the smallest reduced cost \bar{c}^* , hence

Now,
$$\bar{z} + \bar{c}^* \kappa \leq z^* \leq \bar{z}$$

In the optimum solution of the MP, $\bar{c}^* = 0$ for the basic variables and the bounds close. When the objective already is a sum of variables that is $c = 1$, we use z^* instead of κ and obtain the improved lower bound

i.e.
$$\bar{z} / (1 - \bar{c}^*) \leq z^*$$

For $c \geq 0$, Farley proposes a more general lower bound at the expense of a slightly increased computation effort. [5]

Let
$$j' \in \arg \min_{j \in J} \{ c_j / \bar{u}_j a_j \mid u a_j > 0 \}$$

Then
$$\bar{z} + c_{j'} / \bar{u}_j a_j \leq z^* \leq \bar{z}$$

Chapter 4: Branch-and-Price Algorithms

Even with the stronger LP relaxations, optimal solution to the LP relaxation may not give the optimal solution to the original problem. Among the standard approaches of solving integer programs using LP relaxations, the one we are interested uses column generation and branch-and-bound. [6,8]

A very popular algorithm to solve the integer programming problems is the branch and-bound method. In the branch-and-bound algorithm, the total set of feasible solutions are partitioned into smaller subsets of solutions by adding some constraints, usually fixing the value or range of an integer variable. Then the smaller subsets are searched systematically until the optimal solution is found.

The branch operation creates a rooted branch-and-bound tree. The root of the tree is the original problem together with the total set of feasible solutions. When fixing the value or range of an integer variable, several branches grow from its father node and these branches are subproblems with disjoint sets of solutions.

Various notions have been coined for the synthesis of column generation and branch-and-bound such as *branch-and-price* Barnhart et al. and *IP column generation*. Besides the decomposition principles, essentially it all boils down to branch-and-bound. [9,10]

4.1 Generic Branch-and-price algorithm

The branch-and-price algorithm is a hybrid of branch-and-bound and column generation methods. It uses the column generation method to help solve the linear relaxation of the program in each node of the branch-and-bound tree.

Generally speaking, ***Dantzig-Wolfe decomposition*** reformulates the original problem into a master problem and several pricing problems. A column in the master problem is a solution to one of the subproblem. The column generation method is used to generate columns from the pricing problems and then add the columns to the master problem to improve the overall objective of the linear relaxation of the subproblem at the branch-and-bound tree.

Once we have a 'good' formulation for the IP problem the steps for solving using branch and-price is straight forward. Barnhart et al. describes the generic algorithm. [13,14]

- Start with an initial restricted master problem (RMP).
- Solve the RMP using column generation. This may take multiple iterations before no better column can be generated. The columns are generated by solving a subproblem.
- If the LP solution to RMP is already feasible, stop. The solution is optimal.
- Use branch-and-bound technique. Add new constraints to partition the solution space and branch. Apply the same technique of solving LP using column generation at each node of the search tree.

It may seem that branch-and-price involves nothing more than combining well known ideas for solving linear programs by column generation with branch-and-bound. However,

there are fundamental difficulties in applying column generation techniques for linear programming in IP solution methods. [11,15] These include:

- Conventional integer programming branching on variables may not be effective because fixing variables can destroy the structure of the pricing problem.
- Solving these LPs and the subproblems to optimality may not be efficient, in which case different rules will apply for managing the branch-and-price tree.

Barnhart et al. describes the different techniques of handling the above two issues. In the next section we see an implementation of the generic algorithm that gives exact solution to the bin-packing problem. [7]

Chapter 5: Numerical Illustration

Example: Consider example where the raws are 218cm in width, we need to fulfil the following summary of orders with different finals. Let a_1, a_2, a_3 to be the finals of respective width.

i	Quantity Required b_i	Width (w_i) in cm	Finals
1	44	81	a_1
2	3	70	a_2
3	48	68	a_3

We need to decide how each raw should be cut. Many possible ways of cutting a board need not be considered. (any cutting pattern that leaves 68cm or more of waste need not be considered because we could use the waste to obtain one or more 68cm boards).

Following table lists the ways (j) to cut the raws

j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
a1j	1	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
a2j	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	2	3	0	0	0
a3j	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	1	2	3
left	137	67	69	1	56	148	80	12	78	10	8	150	82	14

Solution: Let, x_j = No. of raw cut according to combination j

Objective function

$$\text{Minimize } Z = \sum_{j=1}^n x_j$$

Such that,

$$\sum_{j=1}^n a_{ij} x_j = b_i \quad \forall i$$

$$x_j \geq 0 \quad \forall j \in J$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m w_i a_i \leq W$$

Or, $\text{Min } Z = (x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7 + x_8 + x_9 + x_{10} + x_{11} + x_{12} + x_{13} + x_{14})$

Such that,

$1x_1 + 1x_2 + 1x_3 + 1x_4 + 2x_5$	≥ 44
$1x_2 + 1x_6 + 1x_7 + 1x_8 + 2x_9 + 2x_{10} + 3x_{11}$	≥ 3
$1x_3 + 2x_4 + 1x_7 + 2x_8 + 1x_{10} + 1x_{12} + 2x_{13} + 3x_{14}$	≥ 15
$x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7, x_8, x_9, x_{10}, x_{11}, x_{12}, x_{13}, x_{14} \geq 0$	

Iteration #1 Starting with the restricted master problem.

Let the initial basis matrix be $A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$ $A_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$ $A_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$

The first restricted master problem becomes

$$\text{Min } Z = x_1 + x_2 + x_3$$

Such that, $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix}$

$$x_j \geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3$$

Solving we get,

$$PA = c'_B$$

Where,

$$c'_B = [1 \ 1 \ 1] \text{ and } A = [A_1 A_2 A_3]$$

$$P = c'_B A^{-1} = (1, 1, 1)$$

The first pricing problem becomes,

$$\text{Max } M = a_1 + a_2 + a_3$$

Such that,

$$81a_1 + 70a_2 + 68a_3 \leq 218$$

$$a_i \geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3$$

$$a_i \in Z, \forall j = 1, 2, 3$$

Solution,

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal value for M is 3. (3>1, the iteration must continue)

Iteration #2 The second restricted master problem becomes

$$\text{Min } Z = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4$$

Such that, $\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix}$

$$x_j \geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

Solving we get, $P = c'_B A^{-1} = (1, 1, 0.33)$
 The second pricing problem becomes,

$$\text{Max } M = a_1 + a_2 + 0.33a_3$$

Such that, $81a_1 + 70a_2 + 68a_3 \leq 218$

$$a_i \geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3$$

$$a_i \in Z, \forall j = 1, 2, 3$$

Solution,
$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal value for M is 3. (3 > 1, the iteration must continue)

Iteration #3 The third restricted master problem becomes

$$\text{Min } Z = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5$$

Such that,
$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \\ x_5 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x_j \geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$$

Solving we get, $P = c'_B A^{-1} = (1, 0.33, 0.33)$

The third pricing problem becomes,

$$\text{Max } M = a_1 + 0.33a_2 + 0.33a_3$$

Such that, $81a_1 + 70a_2 + 68a_3 \leq 218$

$$a_i \geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3$$

$$a_i \in Z, \forall j = 1, 2, 3$$

Solution,
$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal value for M is 2. (2 > 1, the iteration must continue)

Iteration #4 The fourth restricted master problem becomes.

$$\text{Min } Z = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6$$

Such that,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \\ x_5 \\ x_6 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x_j \geq 0, \forall j = 1,2,3,4,5,6$$

Solving we get, $P = c'_B A^{-1} = (0.5, 0.33, 0.33)$

The fourth pricing problem becomes,

$$\text{Max } M = 0.5a_1 + 0.33a_2 + 0.33a_3$$

Such that, $81a_1 + 70a_2 + 68a_3 \leq 218$

$$a_i \geq 0, \forall j = 1,2,3$$

$$a_i \in Z, \forall j = 1,2,3$$

Solution,

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal value for M is 1.16. (1.16 > 1, the iteration must continue)

Iteration #5 The fifth restricted master problem becomes

$$\text{Min } Z = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4 + x_5 + x_6 + x_7$$

Such that,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 3 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \\ x_5 \\ x_6 \\ x_7 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x_j \geq 0, \forall j = 1,2,3,4,5,6,7$$

Solving we get, $P = c'_B A^{-1} = (0.5, 0.33, 0.25)$

The fifth pricing problem becomes,

$$\text{Max } M = 0.5a_1 + 0.33a_2 + 0.25a_3$$

Such that, $81a_1 + 70a_2 + 68a_3 \leq 218$

$$a_i \geq 0, \forall j = 1,2,3$$

$$a_i \in Z, \forall j = 1,2,3$$

Solution,
$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal value for M is 1 (The iteration must terminate)

The optimal basis are.
$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 & 1 \\ 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal solution for the cutting stock problem is
$$1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + 10 \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + 24 \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Having an optimum value of 35.

Finding a Good Initial Solution : In solving the cutting-stock problem with delayed column generation, it is desirable to begin with a near-optimal basic feasible solution: if the initial value of the objective function is close to the optimum value, then the number of iterations required to reach the optimum is likely to be small.

j	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
a1j	1	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
a2j	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	2	2	3	0	0	0
a3j	0	0	1	2	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	1	2	3
left	137	67	69	1	56	148	80	12	78	10	8	150	82	14

In the above example if the initial basis could have been taken as shown in **bold letters** instead of *italics*. The iteration could have terminated in the second iteration itself. (selected on the basis of maximum number of finals that can be cut from the rows)

Iteration #1 Starting with the restricted master problem.

Let the initial basis matrix be

$$A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad A_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad A_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 3 \end{bmatrix}$$

The first restricted master problem becomes

$$\text{Min } Z = x_1 + x_2 + x_3$$

Such that,
$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x_j \geq 0, \forall j = 1,2,3$$

Solving we get,

$$PA = c'_B$$

$$c'_B = [1 \ 1 \ 1] \text{ and } A = [A_1 A_2 A_3]$$

$$P = c'_B A^{-1} = (0.5, 0.33, 0.33)$$

The first pricing problem becomes,

$$\text{Max } M = 0.5a_1 + 0.33a_2 + 0.33a_3$$

Such that,

$$81a_1 + 70a_2 + 68a_3 \leq 218$$

$$a_i \geq 0, \forall j = 1,2,3$$

$$a_i \in Z, \forall j = 1,2,3$$

Solution,

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal value for M is 1.16. (1.16 > 1, the iteration must continue)

Iteration#1 : Solution using Branch and Bound (Branch and Price Method)

(a_i can only take integral values)

Column corresponding to $[1 \ 0 \ 2]^T$ must enter the basis as it corresponds to $M > 1$.

Now,

$$B^{-1}b = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{3} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{3} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 88 \\ 9 \\ 144 \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus, column corresponding to $[0 \ 0 \ 3]^T$ is the leaving basis, (Ratio Test) now the new basis are

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Iteration #2 The second restricted master problem becomes.

$$\text{Min } Z = x_1 + x_2 + x_3 + x_4$$

Such that,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 3 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_4 \end{bmatrix} \geq \begin{bmatrix} 44 \\ 3 \\ 48 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$x_j \geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

Solving we get,

$$P = c'_B A^{-1} = (0.5, 0.33, 0.25)$$

The second pricing problem becomes,

$$\text{Max } M = 0.5a_1 + 0.33a_2 + 0.25a_3$$

Such that,

$$81a_1 + 70a_2 + 68a_3 \leq 218$$

$$\begin{aligned} a_i &\geq 0, \forall j = 1, 2, 3 \\ a_i &\in Z, \forall j = 1, 2, 3 \end{aligned}$$

Solution,

$$\begin{bmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

The optimal value for M is 1 (The iteration must terminate)

Iteration#2: Solution using Branch and Bound (Branch and Price Method)

The optimal solution for the cutting stock problem is

$$1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + 10 \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + 24 \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Having an optimum value of 35.

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